

Table 1. Consensus achievement according to Delphi definition

Delphi round	Statements with consensus ($\geq 70\%$)	Statements without consensus ($< 70\%$)	Total
Round I (n=14)	15	17	32
Round II (n=12)	7	10	17
Overall	22	10	32

Table 2: Expert agreement for all statements in Round I (*statements reaching consensus are highlighted in green*).

Statement	1-3 (%)	4-6 (%)	7-9 (%)
General Principles			
There are no absolute contraindications to single-port retroperitoneal surgery.	21.4%	21.4%	57.1%
Single-port surgery facilitates access and navigation within the retroperitoneal space.	7.1%	0.0%	92.8%
Retroperitoneal surgery should be performed using a single-port robotic platform if available	14.3%	42.9%	42.8%
Retroperitoneal single-port procedures have shown advantages in pain control and length of stay compared to transperitoneal	0.0%	21.4%	78.6%

multi-port surgery.			
Role of the console Surgeon			
Surgeons performing single-port retroperitoneal procedures should have prior experience with multi-port surgery.	7.1%	42.9%	50%
During the initial learning curve of the single port platform, before performing retroperitoneal procedures—especially those requiring anterior access—surgeons don't necessarily need to complete an adequate number of cases replicating the multi-port technique.	28.6%	21.4%	50%
Before performing single-port retroperitoneal surgery, the principal surgeon should complete a dedicated cadaveric training course to familiarize with the anatomical constraints and technical challenges of the approach.	0.0%	21.4%	78.6%
Surgeons performing Single Port procedures for the first time should be proctored during their initial cases.	0.0%	7.1%	92.9%
Criteria for optimal patient selection			
Single-port retroperitoneal surgery is the preferred approach in patients with a history of prior	0.0%	35.7%	64.3%

transperitoneal surgery.			
Single-port retroperitoneal surgery is the preferred approach for patients with BMI>30 and MAP < 3. MAP = Mayo Adhesive Probability	14.3%	42.8%	42.8%
Multiport transperitoneal surgery is preferred in patients with MAP > 3	14.2%	57.2%	28.6%
Lower-pole and mid kidney low-complexity renal masses (whether anterior or posterior) are ideal to start Single-port retroperitoneal surgery	0.0%	21.4%	78.6%
Upper-pole renal masses (whether anterior or posterior) are not an absolute contraindication to Single-port retroperitoneal surgery, especially if "Low-complexity"	0.0%	7.1%	92.9%
High-complexity Upper-pole renal masses can be approached with Single-port retroperitoneal surgery, but it may not be the preferable approach	0.0%	21.4%	78.6%
Redo partial nephrectomy is feasible with Single-port retroperitoneal approach	0.0%	42.9%	57.1%

Techniques and considerations for retroperitoneal access			
Lower anterior access (LAA) is the preferred approach for all single port retroperitoneal surgeries in comparison to the flank approach	7.1%	28.6%	64.3%
Lower anterior access (LAA) diminishes position-related morbidity	0.0%	14.3%	85.7%
Lower anterior access (LAA) provides better control of retroperitoneal structures, and a lower risk of complications compared to the side flank access	0.0%	50%	50%
Lower anterior access (LAA) is associated with accelerated postoperative recovery.	0.0%	35.7%	64.3%
Single-port access to the retroperitoneum is faster than retroperitoneal multiport access and potentially reduces the risk of peritoneal perforation	0.0%	28.5%	71.4%
Initial Set up			
While the “pure single-site” approach is preferred, it is not always feasible	14.3%	14.3%	71.4%
The side-car trocar facilitates combining the 'plus one' advantages with the aesthetic outcomes of a pure single-site approach	7.1%	0.0%	92.9%

A “plus-one” port can be positioned as initial setup or can be added in case of need	0.0%	7.1%	92.9%
Procedure-specific guidelines and best practices			
It is acceptable to remove the specimen without an endo-bag in single-port retroperitoneal RARN	28.6%	28.6%	42.8%
It is acceptable to remove the specimen without an endo-bag in single-port retroperitoneal RAPN	14.3%	28.6%	57.1%
During single-port retroperitoneal surgery, LNs should be removed with endo-bag	30.8%	38.5%	30.8%
Postoperative management and patient outcomes			
Single-port retroperitoneal surgery allows for a safe early discharge (24 h) in nearly all cases.	7.1%	28.6%	64.3%
Optimal indication for Upper tract urothelial masses			
The single-port retroperitoneal approach allows adherence to oncological principles during robotic nephroureterectomy.	0.0%	7.1%	92.9%
An adequate LND template can be achieved during single-port retroperitoneal robotic nephroureterectomy.	0.0%	28.6%	71.4%
It is acceptable to remove the specimen without an	35.7%	7.1%	57.2%

endo-bag in single-port retroperitoneal RANU			
The SP platform provides enhanced flexibility for multiquadrant surgical approaches, including robot-assisted nephroureterectomy (RANU) with bladder cuff excision.	0.0%	7.1%	92.9%
Placing a purse-string bladder stitch before the dissection of the bladder cuff is feasible during single-port RANU but is optional if a clip is positioned distal to the lesion.	21.4%	21.4%	57.2%

Table 3: Expert agreement for all statements in Round II (statements reaching consensus are highlighted in green). The statements are presented as revised following discussion and rephrasing, and therefore correspond to those effectively voted on in the second round.

Statement	1-3 (%)	4-6 (%)	7-9 (%)
General Principles			
There are no mandatory contraindications to use single-port in retroperitoneal robotic surgery	0%	0%	100%
Retroperitoneal surgery should be preferably performed using a single-port robotic platform when available	17%	8%	75%

Role of the console Surgeon			
Surgeons performing single-port retroperitoneal procedures should have prior experience with multi-port surgery	17%	8%	75%
Surgeons performing single-port retroperitoneal procedures should have prior experience with multi-port retroperitoneal surgery	84%	0%	16%
Criteria for optimal patient selection			
Single-port retroperitoneal surgery is the preferred approach in patients with a history of prior transperitoneal surgery	0%	0%	100%
Single-port retroperitoneal surgery is the preferred approach for patients with MAP < 3	8%	0%	92%
Single-port retroperitoneal surgery is the preferred approach for obese patients	33%	8%	60%
Redo partial nephrectomy is feasible with Single-port retroperitoneal approach	0%	0%	100%

Techniques and considerations for retroperitoneal access			
Lower anterior access (LAA) is the preferred approach for all single port retroperitoneal surgeries in comparison to the flank approach	25%	17%	58%
Lower anterior access (LAA) provides better control of most of the retroperitoneal structures, and a lower risk of complications compared to the side flank access.	25%	8%	67%
Lower anterior access (LAA) is associated with accelerated postoperative recovery compared to the side flank approach	0%	16%	84%
Initial Set up			
Procedure-specific guidelines and best practices			
It is acceptable to remove the specimen without an endo-bag in single-port retroperitoneal RARN	75%	0%	25%
It is acceptable to remove the specimen without an endo-bag in single-port retroperitoneal RAPN	25%	0%	75%
During single-port retroperitoneal	50%	0%	50%

surgery, LNs should be removed always with endo-bag			
Postoperative management and patient outcomes			
Single-port retroperitoneal surgery allows for a safe early discharge (24 h) in most cases	0%	0%	100%
Optimal indication for Upper tract urothelial masses			
It is acceptable to remove the specimen without an endo-bag in single-port retroperitoneal RANU	92%	0%	8%
Placing a purse-string bladder stitch before the dissection of the bladder cuff is preferable during single-port RANU	16%	8%	6%